

THE ALIBABA CASE AND THE ANTITRUST ACT OF CHINA

Kefei Wang,

Trinity College

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I. Introduction

On April 10, 2021, the China State Administration for Market Regulation made an administrative penalty decision as per stipulated legislation, ordering Alibaba Group to stop illegal behavior and imposed a fine of 4% of its 2019 sales within China of 457.512 billion yuan, totaling 18.228 billion yuan.¹ This penalty is the highest penalty the China government had ever imposed in the antitrust field. The Alibaba Group did not pose any objections and stated that they would accept the penalties and follow the following instructions provided by the SAMR.²

What Alibaba has done was not news. Since 2012, merchants began to complain that Tianmao, Alibaba's B2C platform, forbid them to operate the store on other competitive platforms or join their promotional events. Although Alibaba denies those charges and claimed they only "enforcing management" toward merchants on their platform, merchants said that Tianmao coerced them in quitting vents on another platform, or their store on Tianmao might be shut

¹ SAMR, The State Administration for Market Regulation (SAMR) has imposed administrative penalties on Alibaba Group Holding Limited for its "two-for-one" monopoly in the online retail platform services market in China, http://www.samr.gov.cn/xw/zj/202104/t20210410_327702.html.

² See, Jinwei ZHANG, Administrative Penalty Decision of Anti-Monopoly Investigation 4 (2021).

down.³ However, it was not until 2015 that Alibaba's actions first came to official attention because of a lawsuit raised by Jingdong Group, accusing Tianmao of illicit competition.⁴ In 2017, a first instance decision was made by Beijing Municipal High People's Court, but Tianmao appealed on jurisdiction.⁵ Until 2019, two companies were still struggling with the jurisdiction issue, and the case was still ongoing.⁶ The only response from SAMR is an article posted on their media, calling for E-commerce complaints to restrict their competition under the law.⁷ It was until 2020, SAMR finally started an investigation. Based on their investigation, since 2015, to limit the development of other competitive platforms and maintain and consolidate its market position, Alibaba has abused its dominant position in the market of online retail platform services in China and implemented the "two-for-one" practice by prohibiting operators on the platform from opening stores on other competitive platforms and participating in promotional activities

3 See, Yuan Ma, Tmall and Jingdong force suppliers to choose one over the other Analysis says e-merchants should not catch the traditional retail "stink", China Daily (2012), http://www.chinadaily.com.cn/dfpd/jingji/2012-10/15/content_15818493.htm (last visited Jul 31, 2021).

4 See, haixuan Wen, "Double Eleven" Approaches "Jingdong" Sues "Tmall" for Unfair Competition - China Courts, China courts.com(2015), <https://www.chinacourt.org/article/detail/2015/11/id/1742238.shtml> (last visited Aug 1, 2021).

5 See, Yanfang Wang, Zhejiang Tmall Network Co., Ltd. and Zhejiang Tmall Technology Co., Ltd. Second-instance civil ruling in dispute over abuse of market dominance(2019), <https://wenshu.court.gov.cn/website/wenshu/181107ANFZ0BXSK4/index.html?docId=37bfa7edb44920ab47aae100c0d3d4> (last visited Jul 31, 2021).

6 Id.

7 See, Wenming Zhu, E-commerce competition should comply with the legal bottom line (2015), <http://www.ipraction.gov.cn/article/xwfb/mtgd/202004/162638.html> (last visited Jul 31, 2021).

on other competitive platforms, limiting the operators on the platform to trade within Alibaba only, and guaranteeing the implementation of the practice with various incentives and penalties. Due to such behaviors, Alibaba was accused of violation of Article 17(1)(4) of the Anti-Monopoly Law, stipulating that "without justifiable reasons, the counter-party to a transaction is limited to trading with it only," constituting an abuse of dominant market position.⁸

Although the People's Daily, the China official media posed an article after the start of the investigation, claiming that "This investigation does not mean that the country's attitude of encouraging and supporting the platform economy has changed, but precisely for better regulating and developing the platform economy, guiding and promoting its healthy development."⁹, rise surrounding the Alibaba case might be an indicator that China is going to act toward the over-development of "gigantic internet companies." Moreover, on December 11, 2020, the meeting of the Politburo of the Chinese Communist Party required the country to boost the anti-monopoly act and prevent the disorderly expansion of capital.¹⁰ Under the circumstances that the old ideology were brought to the front again, China's

⁸ See, Administrative Penalty Decision of the State Administration for Market Regulation(国家市场监督管理总局 行政处罚决定书), (2021).

⁹ See, Qiuyu Wu & Lipeng Lin, Promote the healthy and sustainable development of platform economy standards--Viewpoint--People's Daily Online (2021), <http://opinion.people.com.cn/n1/2021/0410/c1003-32074529.html> (last visited Aug 1, 2021).

¹⁰ See, Xi Jinping presided over a meeting of the Political Bureau of the CPC Central Committee-CCP Member Network, (2020), <https://www.12371.cn/2020/12/11/ART11607682691056871.shtml> (last visited Jul 31, 2021).

regulatory reset had come fast. A report published by the Morgan Stanley report department claimed that “the recent regulatory tightening reflects a shift in China's governance priorities from "growth first" to balancing growth and sustainability – i.e., security, self-sufficiency, and social equality.” At this stage, when China is trying to rebalance the rise in corporate power and the share of labor compensation, some systematic de-rating in valuations for some sectors might occur.¹¹ It also needs to be made clear that the regulatory environment in China tends to oscillate between lax and strict enforcement, particularly in emerging sectors. In the lax enforcement stage, local government support, a pro-growth mentality and commercial interests combine to contribute to regulatory lag in emerging sectors. While when public opinion and/or financial stability indicators suggest that problems are imminent, the top leadership switches gears and opens up to a strict regulatory model, quickly mobilizing all administrative resources to reorient policy controls and strengthen regulatory capacity.¹² This pattern has affected several sectors before, including but not limited to mining (2006-2009), dairy (2008-2010), high-end restaurants and alcohol (2013-2014), irrational capital outflows, etc. And now, a series of government actions are clearly signaling that regulation of the tech giants is imminent or has already begun.

11 See, Robin Xing et al., *China's Regulatory Reset* (2021). p. 10

12 *Id.*, 11

This Note will discuss the allegations against Alibaba and its reaction and possible actions the Chinese government took in the anti-monopoly area. This Note will also evaluate that procedure in detail and introduce the ideology explaining the Chinese government's efforts and whether they were proper and adequate.

Regardless of the difficulties, enforcing antitrust laws in China's new internet domination companies will increase in terms of complexity. The relevant departments need to reevaluate traditional measures of market power to serve China's industry better. This difficulty in enforcement has created the Alibaba case will continue as the internet companies already connected them with every detail of people's lives and became an irreplaceable part of it. Finally, this Note will suggest and evaluate some possible changes to the enforcement policy.

For explaining the cause of monopoly, Milton Friedman and Libertarianism is a good ideology to introduce. As an idea that embraces freedom as a core principle, libertarianism believed that a person has absolute freedom to do whatever he wants to do without infringing on the person or property of others, and, when discussing the economy, they also believe that individuals have the right to choose products and services and should not be subject to government licensing restrictions or state-mandated monopolies.¹³ In Friedman's book *Capitalism and Freedom*, he precisely introduced the cause of monopoly, and his

¹³ See. Encyclopedia of Capitalism, (2004) p. 492

theory perfectly fits the Alibaba case. However, libertarianism's laissez-faire approach to monopolies does not seem to be an appropriate one. And when it comes to discussing how to place limits on monopolies, a new supporting theory is required. Dr. Samuel Gregg introduced morals into economy and law and provided us a new perspective on enforcing the law under a free society. His idea is to create the right way to restrain some behavior and be used as a core philosophy to legislation. To solve the already existed monopoly collaborations, the theory does not achieve the ends. Instead, behavioral economy, the economy idea influenced by psychology and cognitive science, might provide a clear insight into how the market economy works and how public choices are made by exploring the social, cognitive, and emotional factors behind the economic decisions made by individuals and groups. The approach based on this theory can gently but effectively stop the uncontrolled expansion of monopolies and thus give rise to a better market environment.

II. The Alibaba Group

The Alibaba Group was founded on June 28, 1999, in Hangzhou, Zhejiang Province. It is now a multinational technology company specializing in e-commerce, retail, Internet, and technology. It started by focusing on providing business-to-business sales service (1688.com). In May 2003, Taobao.com, the consumer-to-consumer sailing platform, was created and soon dominated the market. In April 2003, Alibaba's business-to-consumer platform Tianmao was

established. It has expanded into electronic payment services, financial services, shopping search engines, and cloud computing services¹⁴. The monopoly facts of Alibaba were long-lasting. Since 2008, Taobao, a subsidiary of Nasdaq-listed Alibaba, was a monopolizer in online C2C commerce, holding 84.4% of market shares. The existence of Taobao and Tianmao changed people's shopping habits in China, shifting them from physical stores to online shopping.

For decades, the expansion of Alibaba Group was supported by the China government. However, that relationship appeared to have ended in 2020. The China government banned the Ant group, one of the significant financial filial of Alibaba, from penetrating the market. On November 11, four national departments had a conversation with Jack Ma and two other executives from the Ant Group to supervise and guide Ant Group to implement financial regulation, fair competition, and protection of the legitimate rights and interests of consumers per the principles of marketization and the rule of law, and regulate the operation and development of financial business.¹⁵ On December 24, SAMR started the anti-monopoly investigation toward Alibaba, and in April 2021, the anti-monopoly penalties were enacted.¹⁶

A. Investigation of Alibaba

¹⁴ See, Alibaba Group History, , <https://www.alibabagroup.com/en/about/history?year=1999>

¹⁵ See, Four departments jointly interviewed relevant personnel of Ant Group, (2020), http://www.csrc.gov.cn/pub/newsite/zjhxwfb/xwdd/202011/t20201102_385514.html

¹⁶ *Id.* 8

Based on the report, SAMR launched an investigation into the alleged abuse of market dominance by Alibaba based on the Anti-Monopoly Law of the People's Republic of China (hereinafter referred to as the "Anti-Monopoly Law") since December 2020.

On April 6, 2021, following the provisions of the Administrative Punishment Law of the People's Republic of China (hereinafter referred to as the "Administrative Punishment Law"), the Agency served Alibaba with the Notice of Administrative Punishment, informing it of the facts of the suspected violation of the Anti-Monopoly Law, the proposed administrative punishment decision, reasons and basis, and its right to make statements, pleadings, and request for a hearing as per the law. Accordingly, Alibaba waived its right to state, defend and request a hearing.

B. The abuse of dominant market position Charge

Based on SAMR's investigation, since 2015, to restrict the development of other competitive platforms and maintain and consolidate its market position, Alibaba group abused its dominant position in the market of online retail platform services in China and implemented the "two-for-one" practice by prohibiting the operators on the platform from opening stores in other competitive platforms and participating in promotional activities of other competing platforms. The company also violated Article 17(1)(d) of the Anti-Monopoly Law, stipulating that "without

justifiable reasons, it shall restrict the trading counterparty to trade with it only," constituting an abuse of dominant market position.

The act of Alibaba can be briefly separated into three aspects. The first is to prohibit operators in their platform to open stores in other competitive platforms, the second is to prohibit operators in the platform to participate in other competitive platform's promotional activities, and the third is to take a variety of incentives and penalties to protect the "two choices" requirements for implementation.

III. Since 2015, Alibaba has entered into various agreements with some of the core merchants, such as the Strategic Merchant Framework Agreement, the Joint Business Plan, and the Strategic Cooperation Memorandum, which expressly provides that the core merchants shall not enter other competing platforms, focus on conducting their business on the party's platform or use the party's platform as the only online sales channel in China. They should also not consider conducting transactions on their own or by agents through other platforms and require the party's consent to change their existing e-tailing channels to enable the core merchants to operate only on Alibaba's platform. More often, during the signing of relevant cooperation agreements or negotiations on promotional activities, the core merchants are verbally proposed to operate only on the party's platform, and are required not to open flagship stores on other competitive platforms, or are required to downgrade the flagship stores on other competitive platforms to

non-flagship stores, control the number of exclusive franchises on other competitive platforms, take down all goods, not to ship, limit inventory, etc. Since the party has a dominant market position and the operators in the platform have a firm reliance on the party's platform services, the above requirements are highly binding. The evidence shows that the party's oral request not to operate on other competitive platforms has better effects overall.

IV. To attract consumers and increase the sales of goods on the platform, the online retail platform regularly conducts centralized promotional activities every year, such as "Double 11" and "618", which have a significant impact on the sales of goods and become an important node for the online retail platform to carry out competition. To gain a competitive advantage, Alibaba focused on the core merchants on their platform and requested that they not participate in other competing platforms' essential promotional activities. The Alibaba Group used the same way to restrict the merchants from participating in those activities on other platforms using the exact mechanism as they prohibit them open stores on another platform.

V. Alibaba, on the one hand, encourages platform operators to implement the "two choices" requirement through incentive measures such as traffic support, and on the other hand, monitors the situation of platform operators opening stores or participating in promotional activities on other competitive platforms utilizing manual inspection and monitoring through the Internet. With market forces,

platform rules and data, algorithms, and other technical means, Alibaba impose penalties on operators who do not implement the requirements, including reducing resource support for promotional activities, disqualifying them from participating in promotional activities, downgrading search rights, and canceling other significant rights and interests on the platform. The above penalties significantly reduce traffic to the punished platform operators, causing a significant adverse impact on their normal operation. They have a strong deterrent effect, making more platform operators implement the "pick one from two" requirements proposed by the parties.¹⁷

According to these facts, the SAMR conclude that Alibaba's act infringed the legitimate rights and interests of operators in the platform, harmed the interests of consumers, hindered the development of economic innovation of the platform, and does not have a legitimate reason and request Alibaba to stop the illegal act and imposed a fine of 4% of its 2019 sales in China of RMB 4,557.12 million. The Alibaba Group did not voice any objections. On April 11, 2021, the Alibaba Group posted a new Report of Foreign Private Issuer. In this report, they claimed that "We accept the penalty with sincerity and will ensure our compliance with determination. To serve our responsibility to society, we will operate per the law with the utmost diligence, continue to strengthen our compliance systems, and

¹⁷ See, Administrative Penalty Decision of the State Administration for Market Regulation, (2021).

build on growth throughout the innovation." After all, although the amount of the penalty was the highest in China antitrust history, it was not likely to cause any severe influence on Alibaba's business. According to Alibaba's report on May 13, 2021, in the fiscal year ended March 31, 2021, the income from the operation was US\$13,688 million, accounting for only a decrease of 2% year-over-year.¹⁸ The SAMR also did not ask Alibaba to make any other significant concessions except a fine but only ask Alibaba to cease its anti-competitive practices and submit a self-study compliance report within three years.¹⁹ Such a blur of requirements might indicate that the impact on Alibaba might appear indirectly. Alibaba's business has expanded from shopping to logistics, fresh produce, entertainment, social media, travel booking, and many other areas. The conflict between regulatory authorities could have a longer-term impact on Alibaba's business since the SAMR can randomly start investigating Alibaba's companies at any time.

III. The Origin of Monopoly in China

The Chinese government has recently demonstrated its commitment to anti-monopoly, which left us with two noteworthy issues: whether it is necessary to conduct such action and whether their action will effectively restrict the Alibaba Group and perhaps other Internet giant companies in China to stop their

¹⁸ See, Alibaba Group Announces March Quarter and Full Fiscal Year 2021 Results, 49.

¹⁹ See, Administrative Instructions of the State Administration for Market Regulation, (2021).

monopoly act. To answer these questions, we should start from two aspects. One is to study more specifically about monopoly. By analyzing its origin, process, and consequences, Alibaba actually did toward the market in China, and what might be the consequence of its behavior that was not put to a stop can be scrutinized. Another aspect we should focus on is from the perspective of jurisprudence. To analyze the effectiveness of the anti-monopoly act, it is necessary to comprehend the fundamental purpose of the antitrust law or the law to reach a fair conclusion regarding the Alibaba monopoly case.

In general, China's market can be categorized as a free market, at least in the consumer market²⁰. In his book *Capitalism and Freedom*, Milton Friedman identified a central feature of the market organization of economic activity: "The consumer is protected from coercion by the seller because of the presence of other sellers with whom he can deal. The seller is protected from coercion by the consumer because of other consumers to whom he can sell"²¹ However, this characteristic of a free market only exists when effective freedom of exchange is maintained.²² When such freedom was interfered with, for example, monopoly, the absence of choice will block the freedom of exchange. In Alibaba's case, the lack of freedom was more pronounced from the sellers' perspective. Due to the

²⁰ See, The US-China Business Council, China Business Climate Survey (2021).

²¹ See, Milton Friedman & Rose D. Friedman, *Capitalism and freedom* (40th anniversary ed ed. 2002), p. 14-15

²² *Id.* 18

population of merchants on Taobao, one single item might have a dozen sellers. Consumers are not likely to notice any change if some stores were removed or marginalized because, in most cases, there are still going to be plenty of stores to choose from. However, things differ from the seller's perspective. The relationship between the seller and Taobao was complicated. Theoretically, Taobao, as a platform, is to serve its users. However, when Taobao became the dominant platform in China market, it left the sellers with no other option but to continue their business on Taobao, since switching to another platform could entail a decrease in Taobao sales even when their store was marginalized.²³ Taobao's restriction on the channel limited sellers' freedom to sell their goods to another consumer and depriving them of other platforms or channels. These facts made the relationship between Taobao and the sellers on Taobao more like employer and employee. In this manner, Taobao coerced its users to accept their unreasonable regulations, which is precisely one negative impact when monopoly occurred.²⁴ Milton Friedman once raised two classes of problems caused by monopoly in a free society; one is the limitation on the voluntary exchange through a reduction in the alternatives available to individuals.²⁵ The "pick one of two" rule obviously caused that impact.

²³ See, Chongqing Morning Post, Tmall or JD. Sellers are forced to choose one of the two? (2012), <http://news.sina.com.cn/o/2012-10-18/043925381389.shtml>

²⁴ *Id.* 18

²⁵ *Id.* p. 30

Friedman also mentioned that the existence of a monopoly raises an issue of the "social responsibility" of the monopolist. He believed that the monopolist, someone who holds some power, should use those power not only to fulfill his own interests but also "further socially desirable ends."²⁶ In most cases, issues related to social responsibility are not explicitly stated but somehow stem from the perceptions and opinions of most people.²⁷ However, China is a special case. Given the institutional differences between the Chinese government and other countries, there are requirements and regulations regarding social responsibility in China. The economic model adopted in China is called the socialist market economy. There is a central goal in this theory, namely "common prosperity." The central idea is that capitalism can enrich some individuals but will not enrich the rest of the people. Thus, we should allow some to be affluence; then they can head and help the rest, and eventually reach common prosperity. This idea was not written in legislative text, but all chairmen had reclaimed its central idea since 1990. Under the direction of this ideology, Alibaba had received several dividend policies, including but not limited to tax legislation, law enforcement and legislation with respect to labor disputes, and other dividend policy specially designed for "internet giants." In 2019, Jack Ma, the founder of Alibaba, endorsed China's controversial 12 hours a day, six days a week work culture, a culture

²⁶ *Id.* 17, p. 120

²⁷ *Id.* 17, p. 133

common in the Alibaba Group.²⁸ A behavior clearly violating the Labor law that was rescinded suppressed just recently. Another example is Tencent, another internet giant just like Alibaba. China's social media was called "the ultimate winner in Nanshan," as it seldom lost any lawsuit in a local court due to the government's unspoken rules. Those direct and indirect government assistance protected their interests, allowed them to develop with less restriction, and eventually became monopoly cooperation. Cooperation's advantages also boosted their technology advantages, allowing them to maintain a leading position and encourage them to form private collusion.²⁹ Adam Smith says, "People of the same trade seldom meet together, even for merriment and diversion, but the conversation ends in a conspiracy against the public, or in some contrivance to raise prices."³⁰ Although BAT (Baidu, Alibaba, and Tencent) focused on a different area and had rare conflicts, they have developed at least a high degree of agreement on employee treatment. Friedman had listed three significant sources of monopoly: "technical" considerations, direct and indirect governmental assistance, and private collusion. For instance, all three primary sources were

²⁸ See, Serenitie Wang & Daniel Shane, Jack Ma endorses China's controversial 12 hours a day, 6 days a week work culture, CNN, <https://www.cnn.com/2019/04/15/business/jack-ma-996-china/index.html>

²⁹ See, Bijuan Dong, VAT reform brings policy dividends Specialist www.gov.cn (2018), http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/2018-04/18/content_5283541.htm

³⁰ See, The Wealth of Nations (1776), Bk. T, chap. x, Pt. II (Cannan ed. London, 1930), p. 130,

demonstrated at Alibaba. This leads to the fact that monopolies become inevitable.

IV. China's Antitrust Law

Before discussing the effectiveness of the punitive measure, we should understand the purpose of the law. Only when the theory behind the doctrine was clarified can we then analyze the clause and see if it will function as expected. Charles de Montesquieu said, "Law, in general, is human reason insofar as it governs all the peoples of the earth,"³¹ and a difficult task of law is "to support our reason against the impulses of our passions-to guide a reasoning people capable of self-governance but also of self-abasement, without unduly undermining our scope for free choice."³² Numerous liberals, such as Rawls and Hayek, regarded the law as a critical institution, perhaps the key institution of civilization.³³ Hayek argued that the unique thing about law is that no one invented it.³⁴ Instead, law emerges through a process of natural selection, whereby unconscious habits develop into explicit, more abstract rules that embody certain information that we consider before acting.³⁵ In this way, the law allows the legitimate autonomy of each individual to be determined in advance

³¹ Montesquieu, *The Spirit of the Laws*, I. 3.

³² Samuel Gregg, *On ordered liberty: a treatise on the free society* (2003), p. 52

³³ *Id.* p.52

³⁴ *Id.* 31

³⁵ *Id.* 31

while allowing the individual to act freely within the limits of this determination.³⁶ However, Samuel Gregg argues that Hayek's understanding of how the law protects human liberty failed to distance law from the demands of the good and, therefore, integral liberty.³⁷ In his theory, culture and integral liberty are two critical points. Culture is a uniquely human trait. It encompasses everything through which people develop their many physicals, moral, intellectual, and spiritual qualities. Its formation requires human creativity and intelligence, which can be expressed and embodied in various products, practices, and institutions.³⁸ In this category, moral culture is formed by law. Gregg argues that law is in part an expression and a shaper of human culture. Thus, although it might not need to play a primary role in shaping a society's moral culture, it "should not directly promote any activity that damages this moral ecology."³⁹ The idea of integral liberty can be explained as the liberty of self-government. It is the key feature that the law should strive to protect. Since autonomy is necessary for integral liberty, a coherent explanation concerning why the law ought to protect it may be suggested.

³⁶ *Id.* 31

³⁷ *Id.* 22, p. 53

³⁸ *Id.* p. 54

³⁹ *Id.* 22, p. 55

To protect autonomy, the law should function as a coordinator and an educator.⁴⁰ As a coordinator, the law can assist in securing the conditions that help people participate in the basic common good of all community members.⁴¹ It played the role of authority, and in any society, it is necessary to have authority to coordinate their rational choices. Taking the Alibaba Case as an example; What Taobao did to benefit the platform while simultaneously hurts its users' interests, forcing them to limit their market size. It is possible that Alibaba would not have strayed if the regulation did not occur, but reason itself to tell us that monopoly will cause catastrophic results, and some entities need to react to prevent it from appearing. As a coordinator, the law is meant to help every people realize integral liberty and enhance their ability to achieve fulfillment.⁴² In this perspective, SAMR's punishment measured helped achieved the goal of anti-monopoly law.

Regarding the educator role of law, the objection that might be raised on this point is that classical legal theory has always insisted that the law should not be directly concerned with people's motives for obeying that law. Samuel Gregg accepts part of the classical legal theory and points out a significant point of this view of law for autonomy: the law had a pedagogical function. The law provides information that helps people make a reasonable choice and offered a space for

⁴⁰ *Id.* p. 59

⁴¹ *Id.* 38

⁴² *Id.* 38

making a decision under free will. In this case, if we regard the entire Alibaba Group as an individual, the law might violate human autonomy if it forced them not to enact the "pick one out of two" policy. According to Gregg, the right way to do this is to try to "continuing adherence to rules that encourage people to identify, support, and participate in the basic goods, and to discourage people from acting in ways that diminish their self-mastery."⁴³ Unfortunately, the Chinese government's response has been limited to fines and orders to rectify the situation. Such an approach is likely to be ineffective in curbing Alibaba's monopoly over the online e-commerce industry.

V. Possible Solution

Perhaps a better solution to deal with monopoly cooperation is not just punishment and fines, but finding better cooperation avenues, encouraging them to follow the regulations, and providing support if they abided. If restriction were inevitable, indirect punishment is probably a better option. Using penalties to force the cooperation to regulate their behavior might not be that effective since the law cannot close all loopholes, and companies will always try to find ways to circumvent the law while still satisfying their monopoly needs. The best solution should attempt to stop the monopoly act using the force of the market. A healthy market does not have room for monopolies. Thus, a properly regulated market is the right and most effective way to address them.

⁴³ *Id.* 22, p. 61

The theories of the behavioral economy are well suited to building a healthy market environment. In the later part of this paper, I set several points that might help reshape economic policy under the guidance of human behavior.⁴⁴ With a deep understanding of people's motivation and behavior, the traditional policy design and form more effective policies that might help the government and regulators could be improved. Thus, we might be able to improve the way our market appears, halt the monopoly act, and benefit businesses and citizens.

A. Countermeasures

To shape the market to fight against monopoly cooperation first is to change people's recognition of that field and provides direct support to such change. In the Alibaba Case, years of government support toward Alibaba Group had left an impression that the government will continue to support its development and defend its leading position. Such recognition led to a result that new players who attempt to enter this field could not see an opportunity or benefit of competing with Alibaba, preventing the emerging of such companies. One way to stint such recognition back is to inform the public that the field is open for competition or still developing and still had enough market share for new players to enter.⁴⁵

Combining with the notification, the legislators should at the same time make real

⁴⁴ See, Robert D Zettle, Steven C Hayes & Dermot Barnes-Holmes, *The Wiley Handbook of Contextual Behavioral Science*.

⁴⁵ See, *The-Behavioural-Economy-1.pdf*, <https://www.bi.team/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/The-Behavioural-Economy-1.pdf>

changes and prove the credibility and accuracy of their statements with solid evidence. A possible way is to stop the incentives previously given to Alibaba and set up new policies to support new companies trying to fight the Alibaba market. For example, provide government funds or low interests loans toward new companies, reduce tax, or provide other convenience if required. Also, rising tax toward the monopoly cooperation might help bridge the gap between the new company and the monopoly coop.

Financial support is crucial, but financial support with no examination and vetting might entail issues. A mistake easy to make is focused too much on proof and ignoring the need. Vetting is necessary to prevent unscrupulous companies from defrauding the government of support, but unrealistic standards should be avoided. The review criteria should focus more on constructive aspects, such as the new company's objectives, needs, and difficulties. Specific requirements should be flexible enough to accommodate the laws of the market, rather than the other way around. For example, a stiff criterion, requiring the company to hire a certain number of employees or profit a certain amount of money in a period of time, might be an easier way for the legislators to judge. Still, such criteria might force the new company to focus on fulfilling those requirements instead of focusing on their true goal. In some cases, they might be forced to make unreasonable decisions just to fit the doctrine to get the support they need,

interrupting their overall development. Regulations like coverage obligations were needed but should be carefully examined to respect the market.⁴⁶

Besides money and policy-related issues, reputation, credit, and brand effects are also things worth mentioning. The Familiarity effect made people feel more positive toward people, items, or products due to familiarity, which increased the positive feelings. In such a case, the newly formed company was naturally in an inferior position since it was unfamiliar with the consumer and had no guarantee of credibility and reliability.⁴⁷ A lack of confidence can lead to three issues: Consumer reluctance, difficulties in recruiting employees, and hard in attracting sufficient investment. In the absence of government support, these problems can lead to the venture's failure, allowing the monopoly to continue its behavior. But with adequate support, these problems can be solved. The government can provide reputation and cash flow assistance by purchasing necessary goods from the new platform to use their official background to endorse their business. It is also possible for the government to encourage people who are looking for a job to join the newly formed company and permute investments toward it by providing extra supportive policy.⁴⁸

B. Prevention

⁴⁶ *Id.* 43

⁴⁷ *See*, Carole Wade & Carol Tavis, *Psychology* (12th edition ed. 2016), p. 272

⁴⁸ *Id.*, 43

In addition to fighting monopolies by supporting competitive enterprises, the government has the critical task of preventing the emerging of new monopolies. All the policies described above are remedial measures after a monopoly has already occurred, but it is cheaper and more efficient to prevent the existence of monopolies from the beginning. The government or the legislator needs to build a system to identify the companies that are close to dominating the market and enact at the early stage before it is too late. Also, all policies should be tested in a small region before being used throughout the nation. A special district to test new policy might be a good idea. China is more experienced in establishing special zones, and the country's development history has proven the effectiveness of this approach. With all these methods, a monopoly should be restricted, creating healthy market order.⁴⁹

VI. Conclusion

It is easy to see from the Chinese government's recent crackdown on major Internet monopolies that anti-monopoly will be an important part of the future of government in China. This will be a heavy blow to the monopolies that have previously been developing under preferential government treatment. While regulation is more about rebalancing the rise of corporate power and the share of labor compensation, sudden shifts in policy tend to undermine market confidence and can weaken private confidence, thereby damaging the job market. Fortunately,

⁴⁹ *Id.*, 43

regulation of data-rich technology companies, platform companies, and real estate developers is likely to continue to tighten, and industries that fit into China's new economic agenda should continue to be supported, such as semiconductor localization, cybersecurity software, innovative biotech and pharmaceutical companies differentiating drugs, mass consumption/national brands, vocational training and green economy-related investments.⁵⁰ China's political system dictates that when the government decides to intervene, companies are powerless. There is no effective means of resistance for these companies other than to comply with the government's decisions. Recently, Alibaba Group and Tencent Group are in talks to cooperate. It seems that the two long-standing rival monopolies have finally decided to join forces under government pressure, not to fight the government but to cut their losses. And it is easy to see that the anti-monopoly efforts against the Chinese team will not weaken in the future. Although the means currently employed by the Chinese government may not be able to deal a devastating blow to the two monopolies, the government's objective has been achieved: China still needs these two companies, but it needs two controllable "national enterprises" that can make a positive contribution, not in their present state.

⁵⁰ See, Robin Xing et al., *China's Regulatory Reset* (2021).